
Comparative Analysis of Direct Rehabilitation Costs of a Drainage System: CIPP versus Open-Cut Method

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Abstract. The purpose of this paper is to analyse the cost composition involved in a renovation project, comparing the traditional method with a rehabilitation technique using trenchless technology. We will focus specifically on the CIPP (Cured-In-Place Pipe) method and compare its costs with the traditional approach, limited to small diameters, specifically those less than DN 300.

The CIPP method offers several advantages over the traditional method, including lower economic, social, and environmental impact, and is consistent with the principles of environmental sustainability. Industry literature does not typically calculate all the individual costs contributing to the total cost; instead, it often extracts project costs from various case studies, parameterizes them, and compares the results, particularly for small, medium, and large diameters.

In this paper, costs are presented but not calculated, due to the inherent difficulties in identifying specific figures, which goes beyond the scope of this document. To clarify the analysis, some examples of cost composition for common configurations in practical applications will be provided. These examples reflect scenarios typically managed by building managers or network authorities overseeing wastewater, water, and irrigation systems.

The study demonstrates the economic advantages of applying the CIPP method in large urban areas, where indirect costs, in particular, are more significant.

Keyword: cost-effective, drainage renovation, rehabilitation, CIPP costs, open-cut costs, indirect costs, cost construction, social costs, buried pipe.

Acronyms and definitions

CIPP: Technology to provide a cured in place pipe

DN: Nominal diameter

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- Replacement: Complete replacement of a part or entire structure or facility that has reached the end of its useful life or is no longer functional. In the pipeline industry, replacement refers to the removal of an existing pipe and the installation of a new one. This method is contrasted with rehabilitation or repair techniques, where one seeks to repair or rehabilitate the structure without completely replacing it.
- Rehabilitation: All measures to restore or improve the performance of an existing pipeline.

Introduction. All underground transportation networks, such as wastewater, water supply, or irrigation systems, are subject to maintenance due to joint leaks, localized failures, blockages, and structural collapses. Based on the author's personal experience in the technical sector of INAIL Lombardia, whenever one or more of these issues arise, network managers tend to submit a simplistic request for a cost estimate. It is highly likely that the estimate will propose a traditional intervention, which usually involves demolition, excavation, and restoration work. Rarely are trenchless, low-environmental-impact methods suggested. This is due to cultural factors, including work practices and a general reluctance to offer alternative solutions. Additionally, it should be noted that Italian citizens, by and large, seem naturally tolerant of disruptions to road infrastructure. As a result, these advanced technologies have been slow to gain traction in Italy.

Moreover, companies historically tend to favour lower-skilled labour and the use of common equipment, such as excavators, trucks, and non-specialized workers, rather than embracing no-dig technologies. It is also worth mentioning that official price lists often do not include entries for the latest renewal, rehabilitation, or repair technologies for sewage systems.

In this context, the widespread adoption of advanced technologies is significantly hindered, and, as it stands, information on the existence and feasibility of such methods is primarily disseminated by the commercial sector of companies specializing in destructive technologies.

In Germany, where environmental impact is of great concern to citizens, trenchless technologies are much more prevalent.

It is always advisable for property managers to seek assistance from a technical body that can recommend the most appropriate intervention.

A localized repair or complete rehabilitation using trenchless technologies offers the following advantages:

- Immediate site setup and dismantling;
- Significantly reduced intervention times;

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- Low environmental impact (noise, vibrations);
 - Minimal occupation of public space in both time and area;
 - High environmental sustainability;
 - In some cases, no need for municipal intervention permits;
 - No need for permits from the authority overseeing historic buildings;
 - No surface excavation, demolition, or restoration required;
 - No long-term maintenance required for the treated areas;
 - Immediate availability of road infrastructure and public spaces;
 - Limited or no disruption to pedestrian and vehicular traffic;
 - Reduced costs for interventions on small to medium diameters.

In this study, we consider indirect cost components in different contexts, whether the intervention is on a road or within a building, while omitting irrigation sector interventions. The total cost (TC) consists of the direct cost (DC) or construction cost and generalized indirect costs (IGC).

$$TC = DC + IGC$$

It is well known that the construction cost, carried out according to the installation procedure EN 13566-4, consists of the costs of resources, energy, materials, equipment, labour, and, given the quantities and unit prices derived from a price list, it can be calculated. The more challenging task, however, is calculating the generalized indirect cost, as there are various random parameters that make this calculation debatable. For these reasons, researchers, when conducting a cost-benefit analysis, refer to data and measurable results that are inherently less subjective; thus, the economic comparison among different technologies should focus solely on construction costs, excluding monetary estimates of the effects caused by the work process on users or society.

In this study, we will limit our analysis to the components of generalized indirect costs.

Comparison of the costs between trenchless and traditional technology per m of pipe. Hydraulic engineers, whose professional toolkit includes an understanding of the price range for the installation of a lining and the individual price items for the replacement of a pipe using traditional methods, have no doubts in identifying the most economically advantageous method.

Below, we refer to the industry literature, which considers only construction costs. Almost all researchers reference the construction costs of projects, which may or may not take generalized costs (IGC) into account. Construction costs are gathered from a collection of projects completed in previous years, encompassing both trenchless technology and open-cut methods. Data from these studies are extracted specifically for CIPP and

open-cut technologies, even though our focus is exclusively on small diameters (<DN 300).

Zhao and Rajani (2002) provide a normalized comparison across diameters based on the methodology outlined above, involving at least five projects. All costs are expressed in Canadian dollars, using the exchange rate of 1 US\$ = 1.48 CDN\$ for the year 2001.

Average cost of trenchless techniques

Method	\$/mm dia./m	Diameter range [m]		
		Small (300-940)	Medium (960-1830)	Large (960-1830)
		\$/m	\$/m	\$/m
CIPP	1,38	299	531	2654
Open cut	3,85	609	2.314	2225

In the case of a DN 300 sewer collector, the costs are as follows:

CIPP: 414 CAD

Open cut: 1155 CAD

The difference in cost between the two technologies is a factor of 2.79.

Below, we present the curves from the aforementioned researchers related to the rehabilitation of 1 meter of pipe

Increase of CIPP rehabilitation with pipe diameter

The price variation between different diameters is almost linear with respect to the diameter in CIPP technology.

Cost curve for Open-cut method

The price variation between different diameters follows an approximately quadratic curve in open-cut technology. Below, we present another result produced by Kaushal V. et al. (2019), which confirms the linear relationship between construction costs and diameter in CIPP rehabilitation projects and the quadratic relationship in the case of open-cut implementations. This conclusion is reached through a statistical analysis, with a correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.93 for CIPP implementations and 0.96 for open-cut projects. The correlation is positive and nearly perfect, as both variables increase proportionally together.

In addition to statistical considerations, it is noteworthy that the installation price of a new sewer using the CIPP method is lower for diameters up to nearly 2000 mm. According to Kaushal, the costs in US dollars per meter for a diameter of 300 mm are as follows:

CIPP 256 US\$/m

Open-CUT 603 US\$/m

Comparison of the Costs Between Urgent and Planned CIPP Maintenance. Urgent maintenance is always discouraged for drainage systems for the following reasons:

- It does not allow the use of all or part of the building.
- It precludes the option to seek the most cost-effective supplies.
- It prevents the opportunity to find the best repair technician.
- It requires waiting for spare parts during the system's downtime.
- It faces an ever-increasing failure rate in aging systems.

The cost of intervention is 3.6 times higher compared to costs incurred during planned maintenance.

Generalized Indirect Costs. Before concluding this discussion, we would like to present only the components for a potential calculation of indirect costs. If all components could be calculated, it would make sense to apply Life cycle cost LCC methods as the sum of initial cost, repair and maintenance cost and renewal cost of the project to evaluate project alternatives. In any case, this cost consists of four components.

$$IGC = C_i + C_s + C_r + C_a$$

C_i Interference Costs

C_s Social costs

C_r Risk cost

C_a Environmental Impact Costs

Risk costs are subjective and are therefore ignored, as is the environmental cost, which is only relevant for evaluating project alternatives. In contrast, the first two costs, C_i and C_s , are calculated as they are significant both qualitatively and quantitatively, and are also easily calculable. Therefore, the above formula is reduced to:

$$IGC = C_i + C_s$$

where

$$C_i = \beta(C_{mtp} + C_{mc} + C_{tv} + C_{is} + C_{dv}) + C_{pco}$$

$$C_s = \beta(C_{de} + C_d)$$

C_{mtp} Cost of increased travel time experienced by the user

C_{mc} Cost of additional fuel used by the user

C_{tv} Costs for unavailability of parking areas

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- C_{is} Social cost of road accidents
- C_{dv} Cost for uncomfortable travel (various delays)
- C_{peo} Cost for the loss of the original characteristics of the road
- β Multiplicative coefficient dependent on the nature of the work, whether it serves private or public utility

Social costs reflect the negative impacts of construction sites on roadways, while negative economies pertain to interferences with local business activities and residential spaces.

C_{de} represents the cost of negative economies, and

C_d represents the cost of discomfort due to interferences with residential spaces.

Discussion. The total cost of the work is challenging to calculate; however, the calculation of construction costs is part of the professional toolkit of every technician. In concluding this work, it is noteworthy that, according to Kaushal, a 300 mm pipe costs 2.3 times more than a rehabilitation performed using the CIPP method, while according to Zhao-Rajani, the ratio is 3.7 times.

Normative references

EN 752-5:2017 Drain and sewer systems outside buildings - Rehabilitation

EN 13566-1:2004 Plastic piping systems for renovation of underground non-pressure drainage and sewerage networks – General

EN 13566-4:2005 Plastic piping systems for renovation of underground non-pressure drainage and sewerage networks. Lining with cured-in-place-pipes

References

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Declaration of competing interest

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Author biographies

Giacomino Argento is a civil hydraulic engineer specializing in large office building systems and maintenance. In the past, he served in construction procedures for the European Commission. In INAIL he has developed several detailed designs of installations. As a qualified project manager, he oversees public works tenders and bids. His research interests focus on the maintenance of hydraulic systems using non-destructive technologies.